

Editorial

Psychophysiology Escalating in Pakistan

Shamoon Noushad

Advance Educational Institute & Research Centre- AEIRC

Interest within the mind/body relationship is as ancient because it is large, and also the field of physiological psychology is researching and confirming this association. In Developed countries there has been a gap between the allopathic and alternative medical worlds with regard to views on psychophysiology because the allopathic model continuous to differentiate the mind and body as a separate entity, while the alternative medical field opinions confidently on the concept that the mind and body are complexly connected. Now western world has gotten the fact at which the emphasis is more and more on mind/body healthcare. Patients as well as general practitioner are selecting to make use of treatments built upon the holistic models in which psyche (mind) and soma (physical body) are seen as one. They are working to reduce overall stress and to heal various psychosomatic illnesses.

On the other hand in Pakistan there is a huge conflict among psychologist & physiologist, the main reason behind this conflict was that who will own the psychophysiology? While according to book Psychophysiology is the branch of physiology that is concerned with the relationship between mental (psyche) and physical (physiological) processes; it is the scientific study of the interaction between mind and body. A psychophysiological complaint is considered by somatic symptoms that are moderately induced by emotional factors. The above detail provides all the answers for the conflicts in Pakistan.

In previous years several new organizations were formed in the domain of Mind Sciences, which shows that Pakistan has positive interest in this field. But on the other hand these new organization lack reference research papers to support their therapies and it was also seen that most of the therapies developed were the old psychological techniques with new names. It was also found that research frame work is quite week in these areas and therefore we have very few data regarding physiological processes as sleep rhythms, heart rate, canal functioning, immune reaction, and brain performance Techniques, electroencephalograms (EEGs), resonance imaging (MRI), and computerized axial pictorial representation (CAT) scans in this field. While there are many interpretations of what a healthy Psychophysiology science might seem like, these were only few important examples of Psychophysiology tests &

techniques which are required to establish this new field in our country.

When we discuss about stresses, traumas, or emotional states area unit gift, people might expertise physiological unrest. Psychophysiology is the field of science which is proving that therapies that integrate mind/body processes are shown to help the healing processes for varied diseases. Ultimately, such a holistic state exists once internal and mental awareness becomes sturdy enough to make a way of embodiment, balance, and presence in a person's body. The medical aid medical world has achieved nice breakthroughs in human health, notably with relation to the treatment of traumatic and dangerous injuries and diseases.

Medically, socially, and environmentally, a lot of holistic and preventive approach to aid is being sought-after, one that integrates and balances the mind/body relationship. Abundant work is being done to develop new knowledge; the sphere of physiological psychology could be a major contributor to the exploration.

In Pakistan Advance Educational Institute & Research Centre- AEIRC is the first institute which has develop a research division separately for Psychophysiology under the guidance & leadership of Dr. Sadaf Ahmed, an only PhD in psychophysiology in Pakistan, this super women has established a psychophysiology research laboratory in university of Karachi (Public Sector, Government University) furthermore she has also launched the Pakistan first psychophysiology research journal entitled "Annals of Psychophysiology". A variety of psychophysiology professional's courses were developed by her, such as body brain & behavior, Community Mental Health Worker program, clinical psychophysiology program. She has also established free stress clinics & stress evaluation tool for Pakistani population with the objectives to promote professional standards of practice, ethics, and education. Pakistan society of psychophysiology was founded by her & this society is conducting an annual conference to promote this field in Pakistan.

Pakistan has a great potential and people like Dr.Sadaf Ahmed are the key turning point of alternative medical world, which will surely help to make better health care system in this country.